

Piperazinoarylthiocarbamides as Anthelmintics

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Twenty three 1-(β -dialkylaminoethyl)-1-(4'-phenylpiperazino)-3-arylthiocarbamides have been synthesised using appropriate arylisothiocyanate and 3-(dialkylamino)-1-(4'-phenylpiperazino) ethylamine. 3-(Dialkylamino)-1-(4'-phenylpiperazino)ethylamines were prepared from dialkylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride and 1-amino-4-phenylpiperazine. All the compounds were characterised by their sharp m. ps., elemental analyses and ir spectra. The compounds were also tested for their antiacetylcholinesterase activity (*in vitro*) and selected compounds were tested for anthelmintic activity (*in vivo*). Anthelmintic activity was determined against *Hymenolepis nana* in mice. Promising results were obtained which have been discussed.

COMPOUNDS of diverse chemical structure have been screened for their anthelmintic activity, but the piperazine and its derivatives have been reported to possess marked anthelmintic activity¹⁻³ and are in clinical use, e.g. piperazine adipate, citrate etc. Besides piperazine ethylenediamine an open chain analogue of piperazine and its derivatives have also been reported to possess anthelmintic activity⁴. The distance between two nitrogen atoms markedly effects the anthelmintic activity in these type of compounds. Furthermore, when the two nitrogen atoms are separated by a bridge of two carbon atoms, the attachment of the drug to the bioreceptors is facilitated⁵. This might cause an increase in the anthelmintic activity. Arylisothiocyanates have been shown to possess anthelmintic activity⁶. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise 1-(β -dialkylaminoethyl)-1-(4'-phenylpiperazino)-3-arylthiocarbamides, where the two nitrogen atoms are separated by a bridge of two carbon atoms, as possible anthelmintic agents. These compounds were tested for their antiacetylcholinesterase activity (*in vitro*) and anthelmintic activity (*in vivo*) against *Hymenolepis nana*.

Experimental

All the compounds were routinely checked by tlc on silica gel G. Melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. Elemental analysis was found within range. Infrared spectrum was determined using a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

Dialkylaminoethylchloride hydrochloride and 1-amino-4-phenylpiperazine: The compounds were prepared according to reported methods⁷⁻¹⁰.

3-(Dialkylamino)-1-(4'-phenylpiperazino)ethylamine. Dialkylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride (0.01 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.03 mol) in absolute alcohol (50 ml) were cooled

and 1-amino-4-phenylpiperazine (0.01 mol) was added slowly with stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h, cooled, diluted with equal volume of water, and ethanol was removed. The aqueous solution was saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with ether. Ether was removed, a solid mass obtained was recrystallised with alcohol.

1-(β -Dialkylaminoethyl)-1-(4'-phenylpiperazino)-3-arylthiosemicarbamide: 3-(Dialkylamino)-1-(4'-phenylpiperazino)ethylamine and aryl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) in equimolar ratio in benzene (50 ml) were refluxed for 1-2 h. The resulting compounds 1-(β -dialkylaminoethyl)-1-(4'-phenylpiperazino)-3-arylthiocarbamides, were crystallised with benzene/petroleum ether. The compounds synthesised are reported in Table 1 alongwith their analytical data. The ir spectra were consistent with their chemical structure.

Biological studies:

Determination of acetylcholinesterase inhibitory activity: Adult albino rats weighing about 150 g were killed by decapitation. Brains were removed, weighed and 10% (w/v) homogenate was prepared in ice-cold 0.25 M sucrose. The acetylcholinesterase activity was determined colorimetrically using acetylthiocholine as substrate¹¹ (Table 2).

*Determination of anthelmintic activity*¹²: A number of male albino mice were infected with 200 viable ova of *H. nana*. On the 15th day after infection, faecal smears were taken from each animal and were examined under microscope for the presence of ova of *H. nana*. All the animals were marked, weighed and divided into groups of four animals each. On the 17th day animals were fasted. On the 18th day a large single oral dose of the test compound was given. A group of four animals was left untreated as control. On the 19th day all the animals including controls were again fasted and were sacrificed on 20th day. All the worms from the

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TABLE 1—1-(β -DIALKYLAMINORETHYL)-1-(4'-PHENYLPIPERAZINO)-3-ARYLTHIOCARBAMIDES*

Sl. no.	R	X ₁	X ₂	M.p °C	Yield %
1.	OH ₂ -N'-OH ₂	H	H	180	50
2.	OH ₂ -N'-OH ₂	H	OCH ₃	204-5	45
3.	OH ₂ -N'-OH ₂	OCH ₃	H	212-14	55
4.	CH ₃ -N'-CH ₃	H	OH ₂	200	50
5.	OH ₂ -N'-CH ₃	OH ₂	H	208	40
6.	C ₂ H ₅ -N'-C ₂ H ₅	H	H	191	55
7.	C ₂ H ₅ -N'-C ₂ H ₅	H	OH ₂	200	50
8.	C ₂ H ₅ -N'-C ₂ H ₅	OH ₂	H	204	50
9.	N-	H	H	195	50
10.	N-	H	OCH ₃	168	50
11.	N-	OCH ₃	H	200	45
12.	N-	H	OH ₂	164	50
13.	N-	OH ₂	H	174	40
14.	N-	H	H	180	50
15.	N-	H	OCH ₃	168	45
16.	N-	OCH ₃	H	176	85
17.	N-	H	OH ₂	151	50
18.	N-	OH ₂	H	162	45
19.	C ₂ H ₅ -N-C ₂ H ₅	H	H	140	50
20.	C ₂ H ₅ -N-C ₂ H ₅	H	OCH ₃	182	45
21.	C ₂ H ₅ -N-C ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	H	206	40
22.	C ₂ H ₅ -N-C ₂ H ₅	H	OH ₂	170	40
23.	C ₂ H ₅ -N-C ₂ H ₅	OH ₂	H	168	45

* All the compounds showed consistent elemental analysis.

TABLE 2—ANTIACETYLCHOLINESTERASE ACTIVITY OF 1-(β -DIALKYLAMINORETHYL)-1-(4'-PHENYLPIPERAZINO)-3-ARYLTHIOCARBAMIDES

Sl. no.	Inhibition %
1.	25
2.	85
3.	80
4.	20
5.	20
6.	80
7.	25
8.	Nil
9.	80
10.	40
11.	20
12.	25
13.	15
14.	15
15.	15
16.	Nil
17.	Nil
18.	Nil
19.	15
20.	20
21.	Nil
22.	15
23.	Nil

small intestine were collected and the chemotherapeutic evaluation was done on the basis of the number of mice cleared of infection (Table 3).

TABLE 3—ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY OF 1-(β -DIALKYLAMINORETHYL)-1-(4'-PHENYLPIPERAZINO)-3-ARYLTHIOCARBAMIDES AGAINST *H. nana* (*in vivo*)

Sl. no.	R	X ₁	X ₂	Mice survived	Mice cleared
1.	OH ₂ -N-OH ₂	H	H	4/4	3/4
2.	OH ₂ -N-CH ₃	H	OH ₂	3/4	0/4
3.	C ₂ H ₅ -N-C ₂ H ₅	H	OH ₂	2/4	0/4
4.	C ₂ H ₅ -N-C ₂ H ₅	H	OCH ₃	8/4	0/4
5.	C ₂ H ₅ -N-C ₂ H ₅	H	H	4/4	0/4

A single oral dose of 500 mg/kg was given.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds were tested for antiacetylcholinesterase activity at a final concentration of 5×10^{-4} M. These compounds showed upto 40% inhibition. Maximum inhibition was caused by 1-(β -piperidinoethyl)-1-(4'-phenylpiperazino)-3-arylthiocarbamide. Compounds 8, 16, 17, 18, 21 and 23 (Table 2) were devoid of any inhibition while others showed 20 to 35% inhibition.

Five compounds were tested for their anthelmintic activity against *H. nana* in mice (Table 3). Only 1-(β -dimethylaminomethyl)-1-(4'-phenylpiperazino)-3-phenylthiocarbamide showed 75% activity.

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